

A Clustering Analysis of Attacking Football Styles

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Abstract

Identifying and defining styles of attacking football can provide teams with an analytical advantage that can provide both performance and financial benefits. Several studies have attempted to conduct similar studies in this area but with some limitations. This study attempts to discover and define attacking football styles using clustering on a data set containing match events from 1,826 elite professional football matches in the top leagues in England, France, Germany, Italy and Spain. The methodology included dimension reduction using uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP), followed by clustering using a Gaussian Mixture Model. The results found five distinct styles existed in the data set. These styles are defined by counterattacking (cluster 1), direct play using long balls (cluster 2), a high possession ‘controlled’ style (cluster 3), a low- risk high possession style (cluster 4), and an end-to-end style (cluster 5). Beyond this, there was clearly the presence of one style of attacking play that led to greater success than the others. There was no style that was particularly prevalent amongst teams that performed poorly over the period from which the data was taken.

Declaration

No portion of the work referred to in the dissertation has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or other institute of learning.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Association football, henceforth referred to as football, is the most popular sport in the world by fan base (Raudonius and Allmendinger, 2021). The ‘Big five’ European football leagues recorded revenues of €15.6bn in 2017/18, showing just how important a business operation the sport is (Deloitte, 2022). It is therefore not surprising that teams are increasingly willing to try different things to gain an advantage over their rivals and data analytics is one avenue through which this can be attempted. Data science in football and the field of football analytics began with the collection of statistics by hand in the 1950s (Pappalardo et al., 2019). However, simple statistics have limited use in this field. They fail to capture the complex interactions between players during a game (Van Haaren et al., 2015). Technological advances have allowed companies and teams to track match events at a much higher granularity; the data that exists today does not just say how often something occurred, but when, where and how it occurred (Van Haaren et al., 2015). This has allowed much more sophisticated analysis techniques to be used to gain insight.

Algorithms can be applied to these data to address problems such as evaluating performance and discovering tactics (Pappalardo et al., 2019). This development has provided great opportunity for analysis. Of research in this area, there have been several attempts to address the playing styles of teams that exist in football. Game style has been defined as the characteristic playing pattern of a team during games (Hewitt et al., 2016). An attacking style has been defined as the general behaviour of the whole team to achieve the attacking objectives of the game (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016). In football, it is common for teams to be referred to as their style as much as their results and the term ‘playing style’ is at the core of much football discussion and coaching, but the meaning of these styles is often implicit, subjective, and not based on robust, quantifiable research (Hewitt et al., 2016). Using clustering, these styles can be discovered and quantified, providing robust definitions that can inform football discussion (Lago-Peñas et al., 2017; Muller, 2022; Fernandez-Navarro et al.,

2016).

The purpose of this study is to build on existing research in this area and address the shortcomings that exist in prior studies. This study seeks to discover whether distinct styles of attacking football exist in this data set and how these can be defined and quantified using data processing and machine learning methods. This study will provide a framework and methodology for carrying out similar research that can be applied to data beyond the specific data set used here. After this, the analysis will look to discover if any relationship exists between the playing style of a team and its league performance, country in which it plays and other contextual factors. The data being used contains the event data for all matches in the 2017/18 season for five leagues: the Premier League (England), Ligue 1 (France), Serie A (Italy), Bundesliga (Germany) and La Liga (Spain) and is discussed in further detail in Chapter 3.

The structure of this dissertation is as follows. Chapter 2 covers the background of this topic, discusses related work, and summarises the existing status of academic progress in this area. Chapter 3 provides a detailed description of the data used in this study. Chapter 4 explains in detail the questions guiding this research, as well as a technical review of the methodology applied. Chapter 5 contains the results from the machine learning methods used. Chapter 6 carries out the analysis of attacking styles and seeks to answer the research questions proposed in Chapter 4. Chapter 7 concludes this dissertation.

Chapter 2

Background

Several attempts have been made to cluster styles of football, some addressing overall playing styles (meaning both attacking and defending are included) while others focused on attacking styles of play. These attempts vary due to differing definitions of attacking football and methodologies, as well as the nature of the data being used. Beyond the articles that address the specific issue of using clustering to identify team styles, clustering is used in several other areas of football data analysis, as well as several other sports. As well as this, the definition of attacking football has been addressed in the literature often. These three areas cover the scope of literature pertaining to this research. Despite the prevalence and availability of existing research, studies that describe and measure playing styles are lacking (Lago-Peñas et al., 2017).

2.1 What is Attacking Football?

Much literature in this area aims to develop a definition of attacking football and create some performance indicators that make up attacking football. The definitions and variables included in these studies vary greatly. These decisions in the literature can be used as a foundation with which to select variables for this study. Passes, possession, shots and crosses are common across most sources considering attacking football (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016; Lago-Peñas et al., 2017). *Clustering Styles of Premier League Teams Attacking Play – Proform AFC* (2017) focuses solely on attacking football. This research uses fairly simplistic event count data to define attacking football. These include numbers of shots, passes (long and short), wing play, dribbles, crosses, open play shots and set piece shots. Furthermore, there is no use of spatial or temporal data. Spatial data informs where an event takes place on the pitch, as well as the direction of the event while temporal data informs the start and end times of an event happening. These data can provide a higher level of detail to analysis. Interestingly, Muller (2022) omits shooting statistics as part of attacking

Table 2.1: Attacking Football Statistics Used by Muller (2022)

Possession	Field Tilt (attacking touches per 100 combined attacking touches)
	Build-up (<40-yard passes per 100 goalkeeper pass attempts)
	Offsides per 100 pass attempts
	Through-balls per 100 penalty area entries
	Crosses per 100 penalty area entries
Passing	Accuracy (pass completion rate)
	Directness (progressive yards per 100 total passing yards)
	Height (headed passes per 100 pass attempts)
	Length (long passes per 100 pass attempts)
	Switches per 100 pass attempts
Carrying	Directness (progressive yards per 100 total carrying yards)
	Dribbling (dribble attempts per 100 pass attempts)
	Lost balls (mis-controls and dispossessions per 100 pass attempts)

football, instead focusing on how a team plays prior to shooting on goal. These are shown in *Table 2.1* and use statistics belonging to three main areas: possession, passing and carrying. This develops count data into percentages, enabling easier comparisons between teams of different abilities who may have significantly different event count data despite playing similar styles. These metrics also place a big emphasis on spatial data, particularly identifying movement from the team’s goal to that of the opposition. Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016) have a different selection of attacking variables, focusing on three areas: possession, passing and shots. These are overall possession of the ball; possession of the ball in the defensive, middle and attacking thirds; possession of the ball in the centre of the pitch; possession of the ball in wide areas; direction of passes (forwards, sideways or backwards); passes from the defensive third to the middle third; passes from the defensive third to the attacking third; crosses; and shots. As shown by the variables included, Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016) place high importance on using spatial data of events to discover tactics. Other research contains aspects of attacking football that can contribute to this area. Hamilton (2013), for example, proposes a definition of match tempo beyond just possessions per team. This is done by including time- and space-stamped data. The speed of a possession is defined as where d is the distance the ball covers in time t and k is the number of touches of a ball in a possession. This can then be used to determine the average tempo over N possessions for a match:

Determining the average tempo for a team over the course of a season can be a useful insight into its attacking style. Harkins (2022) states that single-event metrics do not effectively capture important context. To address this, Harkins cites ‘direct speed’ as a statistic that can be calculated from sequences, defined as “the number of metres that the ball travels (when measuring directly up-field), divided by the total time of the

sequence”. Combining events data into sequences and possessions and then calculating direct speed can reveal much more about the attacking style of play of a team than simple metrics such as shots, passes or possession alone. Furthermore, Kawasaki et al. (2019) work on using network analysis on passing networks highlights a way to quantify passing styles in the research. Memmert et al. (2017) work through three methods of analysing position data in one game. They highlight the importance of positional data in developing collective performance indicators that can describe the dynamics of a match. They also list potential performance indicators for performance based on position data, such as calculating formation based on mean of player positions, as well as using Voronoi cells to model space control. These indicators provide a good starting point from which to explore using positional data as well as suggesting a method for carrying out the analysis. One thing to consider when applying this to research is the type of positional data available. This paper uses player positional data for all times during the game. The dataset I will be working on only has the temporal and spatial data for each match event (e.g. where the ball is) so some of the techniques listed are beyond the scope of this research.

The resulting styles from the clustering will ultimately depend on the performance indicators chosen (Clijmans, 2021). Using a combination of the above indicators should provide a comprehensive description of the attacking style of a team.

In terms of how these variables manifest themselves on the pitch, there are five main styles of football in the literature: direct, possession, counterattacking, total football, and crossing (Bangsbo and Peitersen, 2000; Reilly, 2011). Of these, counterattacking, total football, and crossing styles have not been defined with performance indicators (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016). This shows a gap in the understanding of attacking football on a quantitative level and demonstrates an area to which this research can contribute.

2.2 Identifying Styles of Play Using Clustering

Papers specifically using clustering to identify styles of football are Muller (2022), Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016), Lago-Peñas et al. (2017), Decroos et al. (2018) and *Clustering Premier League Team Styles- Attack, Defence and getting the whole picture – Proform AFC* (2018) and will each be discussed in turn. Of these, only *Clustering Premier League Team Styles- Attack, Defence and getting the whole picture – Proform AFC* (2018) focuses solely on attacking football. The clustering method used here is agglomerative clustering, a type of hierarchical clustering that could be effective in this research. There was no attempt at dimension reduction. This work provides something of a foundation on which to build here, the general aim is relevant to the research in

this paper but there are several ways in which the methodology can be improved, as seen in other papers in this area. Muller (2022) used clustering to group the teams in the top five leagues based on their overall playing style, including both attacking and defensive data. The statistics used in this research are more sophisticated than that used by Proform Analytics as Muller uses more detailed data, including spatial data, as mentioned earlier.

The methodology used on this data included UMAP dimension reduction and a Gaussian mixture model clustering algorithm. Muller (2022) identified five main styles of play: controlled, end-to-end, launch squish, counter, and bunker. Differences exist between these findings and that of the five styles of attacking football that exist in the literature: direct, possession, counterattacking, total football, and crossing Bangsbo and Peitersen (2000); Reilly (2011). This suggests either a development in how football is played, or differences resulting from using different input data for attacking football. Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016) also attempted to categorise attacking and defensive playing styles in Spanish and English elite football. This paper used factor analysis to identify clusters of variables to see which performance indicators were commonly found together. This did not seek to identify the styles of individual teams, instead focusing on the performance indicators to discover styles of football. There are several limitations to this work. The sample used does not include a full season for either league (English and Spanish elite leagues), data were collected from two different time periods and some performance indicators were excluded (Lago-Peñas et al., 2017). Lago-Peñas et al. (2017) built upon these limitations and conducted a clustering analysis of football styles in the Chinese Soccer Super League, using the same attacking performance indicators. The methodology used included principal components analysis (PCA) and varimax rotation to reduce the dimensions of the dataset, and then extracted the factors with eigenvalues above 1 to be saved as variables for the data analysis. The resulting factors signified a possession style of play, use of set pieces, counterattacking play and two aspects of transitional play. The teams studied were then analysed against each factor to define their style of play as a combination of the principal factors. One suggestion from Lago-Peñas et al. (2017) is to use context of the match in the analysis but due to the volume of data being used in this research, this is not practical to do.

The most sophisticated approach to clustering attacking football styles comes from Decroos et al. (2018). Decroos et al. (2018) suggest that using event frequency data from an entire match is too coarse a granularity to fully analyse the tactics of a team, instead suggesting splitting each match into phases. As well as this, Decroos et al. (2018) use spatio-temporal data to detect the tactics. The approach in this article was:

1. Split the match into uninterrupted sequences of events where one team has possession.
2. Cluster these sequences according to spatio-temporal characteristics.
3. Rank each cluster according to these characteristics.
4. Search for frequently occurring patterns within each cluster.
5. Develop a function that ranks the patterns according to their expected relevance to each cluster.

This methodology reveals very specific aspects of tactics of the teams analysed. Manchester City, for example, have a clear attacking pattern starting from the right flank. This is the level of detail found in this study and has been applied to three teams. This technique allows analysis of a much higher granularity but at the expense of scalability and tactics that do not necessarily translate to a more general style of play, as is the aim of this research.

Overall, there are several ways to contribute to research in this area. Using data of a higher granularity – that is including spatial, and possibly temporal data – in the analysis will provide results with higher detail in defining styles of play, an area that has been highlighted as lacking in the literature. Furthermore, the aforementioned use of phases also provides a method to increase the detail and granularity of the research.

2.3 Clustering in Other Aspects of Sports Analysis

Beyond studies and methodologies focusing purely on styles of play, much research has been carried out using clustering techniques on a variety of sports and data. Carey and Sormaz (2018) sought to cluster the playing styles of players in the full-back position in football to compare objective playing styles against subjective observations, using a combination of PCA with varimax rotation and agglomerative clustering. Michalczyk (2019) identified patterns in build-up play to discover how each team moves the ball from the defending goal up the pitch. A PCA was carried out initially on passing data and then DBSCAN (density-based clustering on applications with noise) was used as the author wanted to only detect repetitive patterns and ignore passes not made in normal build up settings. D’Urso et al. (2022) “propose a robust fuzzy clustering with noise cluster and weighting system for mixed attributes”. This allows analysis of different types of variables and the weighting system allows the relevance of each attribute to the clustering results to be understood. This particular study focused on clustering football players based on their performance and positional attributes. Coughlan et al. (2019) provide an example from rugby league that used k-modes

clustering to find the most frequent try-scoring patterns in play. Interestingly, this analysis included a variable that represented the strength of the opposition in order to introduce some context into the results, something that was suggested by Lago-Peñas et al. (2017) to be introduced in future football analysis. Behravan and Razavi (2021) suggest a method for estimating football players' values in the transfer market using a combination of clustering and regression. The clustering method used is APSO-clustering, an automatic clustering method that can detect the proper number of clusters and is used to cluster players with others in similar roles.

The above sources provide some inspiration for what techniques can be used.

Chapter 3

Data

3.1 The Football Data Environment

The football data environment consists of three main types of data: box score data, tracking data and event data (Shen et al., 2022). Box score data consists of the score and other summary statistics for a match, such as possession and the numbers of shots and corners. Tracking data describes the 2D location of players on the pitch and the position of the ball. The final type, and the type of the data being used in this research, is match event data. It consists of events that occur during a match and the 2D location of the ball at the start and end of each event. Data availability for scientific research has been a problem in football, limiting the effectiveness of using scientific methods for analysis, and inconsistency in terms of the types of data being used in analysis is a weakness that was found in the literature (Pappalardo et al., 2019). Therefore, the choice of data set to analyse is of high importance for meaningful research in this area.

3.2 The Data Set

The data itself is from Wyscout, a soccer analytics platform, and contains match event data from 1,826 regular season games that took place during the 2017/18 seasons of the elite football leagues in England (Premier League), France (Ligue 1), Germany (Bundesliga), Italy (Serie A) and Spain (La Liga). These are ranked as the most important leagues in Europe and this data set was the largest free and open data set for football at the time of its release (Pappalardo et al., 2019). The match event data set itself consists of 3,071,395 events; each event includes data informing start and end locations (as a 2D coordinate), start and end times, outcome, the player involved, the team to which the player belongs, and characteristics. *Table 3.1* shows the event and sub-event types included in the data-set.

For each event, the data informs the following: event ID, event name, event second,

Table 3.1: Event types and their sub-event types

Event Name	Sub-Event Name	
Duel	Air duel	
	Ground attacking duel	
	Ground defending duel	
	Ground loose ball duel	
Foul	Foul	
	Hand foul	
	Late card foul	
	Out of card foul	
	Protest	
	Simulation	
	Time lost foul	
	Violent foul	
	Free kick	Corner
		Free kick
Free kick cross		
Free kick shot		
Goal kick		
Penalty		
Throw in		
Goalkeeper leaving line	Goalkeeper leaving line	
Interruption	Ball out of the field	
	Whistle	
	Offside	
Offside	Offside	
Others on the ball	Acceleration	
	Clearance	
	Touch	
	Cross	
Pass	Hand pass	
	Head pass	
	High pass	
	Launch	
	Simple pass	
	Smart pass	
	Save attempt	Reflexes
	Save attempt	
Shot	Shot	

match, match period, player, positions (start and end), sub event and team ID. From these events, the data must be transformed into relevant attacking variables that will represent attacking football.

Chapter 4

Methodology

The methodology begins by stating the questions that this study aims to answer. It will then cover data pre-processing, data transformation and the creation of the attacking variables. Following this, dimension reduction techniques will be discussed, focusing on UMAP. Finally, clustering will be discussed conceptually and in relation to the analysis conducted in this research.

4.1 Aims of this Research

This research aims to answer three questions. The primary objective of this study is to calculate whether distinct styles of play can be found using clustering on the data set in question. A secondary aim of this research is, if distinct styles are found, to compare these styles with those that exist in the literature and identify differences and similarities with the findings here. A final aim is to investigate the link between playing style and team performance.

4.2 Data Pre-Processing

The intention of pre-processing is to create the attacking variables that will be used to describe attacking football styles. These are shown in *Table 4.1*. Before creating the variables, there is an additional Teams data set that complements the events used, and this is merged to the events data set using team ID numbers to identify the team associated with each event.

4.2.1 Motivation for Variables

The decisions and motivation for what variables to include were driven mainly by the availability of the data. Any data that is related to a team's superiority or skill

level was removed, such as goals, possession and events resulting from fouls such as free kicks and penalties. This was to ensure clusters and styles are not inherently good or bad, but instead focus solely on the style of play (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016; Lago-Peñas et al., 2017; Muller, 2022). Excluding these variables, the data relating to attacking football include all passing events (cross, hand pass, head pass, high pass, launch, simple pass and smart pass), shots, and on the ball events such as accelerations and touches. Using these, the variables created included the prevalence of each sub event type per event type, as well as other variables inspired by the literature. Directness and accelerations were used by Muller (2022). Categorising passes based on start and end locations was inspired by Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016), as discussed in 4.2.3.

4.2.2 Count Data

The majority of pre-processing involved using count data of various event types. This required attributing each event to the count of the relevant team for both general event types and sub-event types. The percentages of these events were then found by using these counts. This technique was used for all variables to some extent.

4.2.3 Zonal Analysis

The possession and passing variables included spatial data. For these variables, the pitch was split into a grid with three vertical sections and three horizontal sections, as done by Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016). This is shown in Fig. 4.1. Playing from left to right, the defensive third is between 0 and 33 on the x-axis, the middle third is between 33 and 67, the final third is from 67 to 100. Furthermore, the wide areas of the pitch are between 0-19 and 81-100 on the y-axis. These splits are shown by the grid. The area between 19 and 81 on the y-axis is considered the centre of the pitch. This allows events to be categorised based on their coordinates in order to include spatial data in the analysis. For the directness variable, progressive yards refers to distance travelled across the x-axis, while total yards is the euclidean distance between the start and end coordinates.

4.2.4 Data Quality

This data set is supplied by Wyscout, a leading data supplier in football (Pappalardo et al., 2019). Readers are referred to Pappalardo et al. (2019) for a detailed account of the data collection and quality insurance. One drawback to this data set, however, is the presence of erroneous data points. This was discovered when looking at the coordinates of goal kicks, which contains start location values that are impossible for

Figure 4.1: Pitch zones with coordinates.

this event type. This was also found by Shen et al. (2022). For most other event types, there are no coordinates that would necessarily be impossible, making it much harder to identify erroneous data. For this reason, there were no attempts to identify or remove any outliers from this data set but it is worth noting the possibility that there may be limitations to the quality of this data.

4.3 Dimension Reduction

4.3.1 A Conceptual Review

Dimension reduction is a type of data reduction, a process of summarising data by aggregating information (Farcomeni and Greco, 2015). The general aim is to keep loss of information minimised while reducing the size of the data. If done successfully, using the data after its reduction should lead to similar conclusions as using the original data set. The motivations for carrying out dimension reduction are to increase interpretability of results, to increase the effectiveness of further analyses and to create the opportunity to plot, as well as being incredibly important when one wants to find patterns and associations in large data sets and identify important variables (Farcomeni and Greco, 2015). These motivations all apply to this research and explain why dimension reduction will be part of this analysis.

4.3.2 Technique Selection

There are several types of dimension reduction techniques available. The choice depends on what the goal of the dimension reduction is. Principal Components Analysis

Table 4.1: Attacking Variables, descriptions and calculations

Type	Variable	Description	Calculation
Passing	Simple passes	A pass that is not explicitly tagged as a smart pass, a launch, a high pass or a cross	Number of simple passes per 100 passes
	Smart passes	A creative and penetrative pass that attempts to break the opposition's defensive lines to gain a significant advantage in attack	Number of smart passes per 100 passes
	Crosses	A ball played from the offensive flanks aimed towards a teammate in the area in front of the opponent's goal	Number of crosses per 100 penalty area entries
	Passes from defence to attack	A pass starting in the defensive third and ending in the attacking third of the pitch	Number of passes from defence to attack per 100 passes
	Passes from midfield to attack	A pass starting in the middle third and ending in the attacking third of the pitch	Number of passes from midfield to attack per 100 passes
Possession	Directness	The proportion of ball carries that are progressive (directly from one goal to the other)	Progressive yards per total carrying yards
	Possession in defensive third	Proportion of possession that occurs in the defensive third	Percentage of possession in defensive third out of total possession
	Possession in middle third	Proportion of possession that occurs in the middle third	Percentage of possession in middle third out of total possession
	Possession in the final third	Proportion of possession that occurs in the final third	Percentage of possession in final third out of total possession
	Possession in wide areas	Proportion of possession that occurs in the wide areas of the pitch	Percentage of possession in wide areas out of total possession
	Possession in central area	Proportion of possession that occurs in the central areas of the pitch	Percentage of possession in central area out of total possession
	Dribbles	A player carrying the ball without attempting a pass or shot	Number of touches per 100 passes
Accelerations	A run with the ball with a significant speed up	Number of accelerations per 100 touches	
Shooting	Long shots	Shots that take place from outside the penalty area	Long shots per 100 shots
	Close shots	Shots that take place from inside the penalty area	Close shots per 100 shots

Figure 4.2: Variance explained by PCA.

(PCA) is typically the first technique considered when beginning dimension reduction (Waggoner, 2021). PCA works by creating new variables, the principal components, that are linear combinations of the original values (Ringner, 2008). These new variables aim to explain the variance of the original data set, in a smaller number than the original data set. If the variance can be explained with a small number of principal components, these can be used instead of the original variables, thus reducing the dimensions of the original data. While this technique is a commonly used dimension reduction technique, it is inappropriate to use in this research. The number of principal components needed to explain over 95% of the variance of the data set is nine (Fig. 4.2). This does not meaningfully reduce the dimensions of the data set, nor does it provide any of the benefits such as being able to plot the data. Because of this, other methods must be considered. Of the two other techniques that appear in the literature, t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding (t-SNE) and uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP), UMAP performs just as well in visualising the data but preserves much more of the global structure (meaning the distances between clusters are also meaningful, not just the distances between the points within each cluster) than t-SNE (McInnes et al., 2020). For these reasons, UMAP was chosen as the appropriate dimension reduction technique.

4.3.3 Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection

UMAP is a novel manifold learning technique that belongs to the k-neighbour based graph learning algorithms class (McInnes et al., 2020). There are two phases to this technique (Cao et al., 2019):

1. A topological representation of the high-dimensional data with local manifold approximations is constructed and their local fuzzy simplicial set representations are patched together.
2. UMAP minimises the cross-entropy between the low-dimensional representation and the high-dimensional representation by optimising the lower-dimension embedding.

When using this algorithm, there are several hyper-parameters that need to be set. These are the number of neighbours (n) to consider when approximating the local metric, the target embedding dimension, the desired separation between close points in the embedding space and the number of training epochs to use when optimising the low-dimensional representation. The important hyper-parameters are number of neighbours and the minimum distance value. The nearest neighbour value represents a trade-off; a small value will allow the accurate capture of detailed manifold structure at a loss of the big picture view whereas a big value will do the reverse (McInnes et al., 2020). Minimum distance is essentially an aesthetic parameter and determines how spread out data points are when visualised, a higher value resulting in more spread out data points and vice versa (McInnes et al., 2020). The benefits of this method have been mentioned, it preserves global and local structures well, it is computationally efficient and allows intuitive visualisations. The drawback is, however, that there is low interpretability for what the created variables represent. Despite this, UMAP represents an effective dimension reduction technique that lends itself well to clustering analyses.

4.4 Clustering

4.4.1 A Conceptual Review

Clustering is an unsupervised classification technique that aims to group objects in a way that similar objects belong to the same group and objects in different groups are not similar (Rogers and Girolami, 2016). It is unsupervised as the data are not labelled so the model cannot be trained. Clustering, in this context, will allow football teams to be grouped based on their style of attacking play. After this, each cluster should, in theory, represent a distinct style of attacking football. In this way, styles can be discovered, defined and analysed.

4.4.2 Technique Selection

Three clustering techniques were considered. These were k-means clustering, Gaussian mixture models (GMM) clustering and agglomerative clustering. These were chosen

based on their prevalence in the literature and their variety. K-means clustering is a deterministic clustering technique that assigns data points to clusters based on distance from the cluster centroid; GMM uses a probabilistic assignment of data to clusters (Patel and Kushwaha, 2020). Agglomerative clustering is a hierarchical method of clustering. The effectiveness and suitability of these methods were compared and evaluated using Silhouette Score, Calinski Harabasz score and Davies-Bouldin score. These metrics are used as they are appropriate when ground truth labels do not exist, as is the case here. The Silhouette Score consists of two scores: the mean distance between a sample and all other data points in the same cluster and the mean distance between a sample and all other data points in the closest next cluster (Rousseeuw, 1987). A model with better defined clusters will achieve a higher Silhouette Score. The Calinski-Harabasz index defines dispersion as the sum of distances between the points squared. The score is then the ratio of the sum of dispersion between the various clusters and the dispersion within each cluster; again, a higher score relates to a model with better defined clusters (Caliński and JA, 1974). The Davies-Bouldin index calculates the average distance between clusters with the size of the clusters, in order to determine the similarity between clusters; a lower score signifies a more effective clustering model (Davies and Bouldin, 1979). The results of these are discussed in the next chapter with GMM scoring best out of the techniques (see 5.2). For that reason, GMM was chosen for this analysis. Another benefit of using GMM is due to its probabilistic nature. This provides a probability of each data point belonging to the cluster with which it is categorised. To see whether styles exist it is useful not only to see how teams are clustered but to what likelihood they belong. This technique will be explained in detail in the next section (4.4.3).

4.4.3 Gaussian Mixture Model Clustering

A GMM forms clusters based on probability density estimations using the Expectation-Maximisation (EM) function and each cluster is modelled as if it is normally distributed. An expression of GMM is provided by Patel and Kushwaha (2020):

$$p(X) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(X|\mu_k, \Sigma_k) \quad (4.1)$$

The Gaussian density is a component of the mixture model and is given by $\mathcal{N}(X|\mu_k, \Sigma_k)$ in Equation 4.1. Each component k is described by a Gaussian distribution with mean μ_k , covariance Σ_k and π_k , the mixing coefficient, which provides an estimate of the density of each component. K represents the number of components in the model.

The Expectation-Maximisation Algorithm

The EM algorithm is used to maximise the likelihood of the results given by 4.1. Using the logarithm of the likelihood is easier, so taking the natural logarithm of Equation 4.1 gives Equation 4.2 (Rogers and Girolami, 2016).

$$L = \ln p(X|\pi, \mu, \Sigma) = \sum_{n=1}^N \ln \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(x_n|\mu, \Sigma) \right\} \quad (4.2)$$

This is the equation we want to maximise but, instead of maximising L directly, we maximise the lower bound, which will approximate 4.2 (Rogers and Girolami, 2016). The bound that we want to optimise is given by Equation 4.3.

$$L = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K E[z_{n,k}] (\log \pi_k + \log N(x_n|\mu_k, \sigma_k)) - \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K E[z_{n,k}] \log E[z_{n,k}] \quad (4.3)$$

The local maxima of L , the log-likelihood, will correspond to the values of $z_{n,k}$, π , μ_k , Σ_k that correspond to the local maxima of this bound (Rogers and Girolami, 2016). As the EM algorithm is iterative, each of these values will be updated and the process will be repeated until convergence. When this happens, the values will correspond to the local maxima of the lower bound, an approximation for the logarithm of the GMM likelihood equation (4.2). For an in depth explanation of how each of these values is optimised, readers are referred to Rogers and Girolami (2016).

Chapter 5

Results

5.1 Dimension Reduction

The data was reduced using the hyper-parameters in Table 5.1. The results of the dimensions reduction show the data visualised on the two components created by the UMAP algorithm, Figure 5.1.

5.2 Evaluation of Clustering Techniques

Following the dimension reduction, three clustering techniques were used on the data and evaluated according to three metrics: Silhouette Score, Calinski Harabasz score and Davies-Bouldin score. The appropriate number of clusters for each method was chosen by selecting the value that resulted in the highest Silhouette Score. These are shown in Figure 5.2. The results of this are shown in Table 5.2. The GMM algorithm returns the best Silhouette Score and Davies Bouldin Score, while underperforming K-Means slightly on the Calinksi-Harabasz index. Agglomerative clustering returned the worst score by all three metrics. Overall, this suggests GMM is a slightly more effective clustering technique for this data set. When also considering the benefits of using a probabilistic clustering method over one that is deterministic, it is clear that GMM is the most appropriate method for the purpose of this research.

Table 5.1: UMAP Algorithm Hyperparameters

UMAP Hyperparameters	Values
No. of Neighbours	5
Minimum Distance	0.25
Number of Components	2

Figure 5.1: UMAP projection of the data set.

Figure 5.2: Silhouette Scores for No. of Clusters for GMM, K-means and Agglomerative Clustering.

Table 5.2: Internal Validation Metrics of Selected Clustering Algorithms

Clustering Algorithm	No. of Clusters	Silhouette Score	Calinski Harabasz Score	Davies Bouldin Score
GMM	5	0.453	126.0	0.689
K-Means	5	0.451	127.1	0.704
Agglomerative	5	0.429	120.3	0.712

Figure 5.3: UMAP and GMM Clustering Results Plot.

5.3 GMM Clustering Results

The weights in Table 5.3 signify the proportion of data points belonging to each cluster. As shown in Table 5.3 and visualised in Figure 5.3, there are three clusters of similar size, one larger and one much smaller. Clusters 1, 3 and 5 contain 21.98%, 19.09% and 22.84% of the data, respectively. Cluster 4 contains 9.03% and Cluster 2 contains 27.07%. The benefit of using GMM is that one can see the probability that each data point belongs to each sample. Tables 5.4, 5.5, 5.6, 5.7 and 5.8 show the teams belonging to each cluster and their associated probabilities. Furthermore, Figure 5.4 shows how the clusters relate to the original variables selected for analysis, demonstrating the variables that are more prevalent or more lacking for each group.

Table 5.3: Cluster Model Results Summary

Main Result Information					
Model Name		Cluster Number		BIC	
		5		836.86	
Weights of Mixture Components					
Categories	Cluster	Cluster	Cluster	Cluster	Cluster
	1	2	3	4	5
Weight	0.2198	0.2707	0.1909	0.0903	0.2284
Means of Mixture Components					
Objects	Cluster	Cluster	Cluster	Cluster	Cluster
	1	2	3	4	5
X	9.14	12.17	6.93	6.09	9.50
Y	10.52	9.55	11.46	9.28	7.83

Table 5.4: Cluster 1 Teams and Probabilities

Team	Probability (%)
Olympique Marseille	99.9
Real Sociedad	99.8
Bayer Leverkusen	99.8
Eintracht Frankfurt	99.7
Genoa	99.6
Athletic Club	99.4
Celta de Vigo	99.4
Hertha BSC	98.9
Olympique Lyonnais	98.0
Hoffenheim	97.5
Torino	97.4
Atalanta	97.3
Espanyol	96.0
Watford	96.0
Borussia Monchengladbach	95.8
Sevilla	94.0
Saint-Étienne	92.9
Crystal Palace	91.3
Werder Bremen	81.3
Villarreal	65.0
Brighton & Hove Albion	52.8
Chelsea	50.2
Mean	91.0

Table 5.5: Cluster 2 Teams and Probabilities

Team	Probability (%)
Burnley	99.9
West Bromwich Albion	99.9
Everton	99.9
Augsburg	99.9
Hannover 96	99.9
Freiburg	99.9
Deportivo Alavés	99.9
Mainz 05	99.9
Benevento	99.9
Cagliari	99.9
Newcastle United	99.9
Crotone	99.9
Stoke City	99.9
Amiens	99.9
SPAL	99.9
Dijon	99.9
Hellas Verona	99.8
Hamburger SV	99.7
Stuttgart	99.3
Toulouse	98.1
Schalke 04	97.4
Getafe	97.3
Bologna	96.7
Chievo	96.1
Leicester City	91.4
Levante	73.6
Wolfsburg	72.0
Mean	97.0

Table 5.6: Cluster 3 Teams and Probabilities

Team	Probability (%)
PSG	99.9
Liverpool	99.9
Napoli	99.9
Manchester City	99.9
Borussia Dortmund	99.9
Arsenal	99.9
Barcelona	99.9
Bayern München	99.9
Real Madrid	99.6
RB Leipzig	99.6
Internazionale	98.6
Manchester United	98.5
Tottenham Hotspur	98.2
Atlético Madrid	97.9
Monaco	96.0
Valencia	92.2
Lazio	85.5
Roma	81.7
Mean	97.1

Table 5.7: Cluster 4 Teams and Probabilities

Team	Probability (%)
Las Palmas	99.9
Real Betis	99.9
Nice	99.8
Lille	99.8
Juventus	99.6
Köln	98.6
Fiorentina	98.5
Milan	93.6
Sampdoria	89.4
Mean	97.7

Table 5.8: Cluster 5 Teams and Probabilities

Team	Probability (%)
AFC Bournemouth	99.9
Troyes	99.9
Strasbourg	99.9
Swansea City	99.9
Udinese	99.9
Angers	99.9
Huddersfield Town	99.9
Bordeaux	99.9
Sassuolo	99.9
Leganés	99.9
Montpellier	99.2
Nantes	99.0
Caen	99.0
Eibar	98.1
Málaga	97.5
West Ham United	97.2
Guingamp	97.0
Metz	96.0
Rennes	90.6
Girona	86.9
Deportivo La Coruña	84.1
Southampton	56.9
Mean	95.5

Figure 5.4: Heatmap of Clusters and Data Set Average with Normalised Variable Values.

Chapter 6

Discussion, Analysis and Evaluation

6.1 Clusters and their Styles

The primary aim of this study was to identify distinct attacking styles of football in elite football. If this was possible, a secondary aim was then to define these styles and compare them to styles that exist in the literature. The results from the clustering found five distinct attacking styles amongst teams in this data set. Furthermore, the benefit of using a GMM model is that it is possible to see the probability that a data point belongs to each style. In this way, we can see to what extent these attacking styles are clearly defined and the results suggest that they are clearly defined. This can be seen as the average probability that a team belongs to a cluster is over 90% for all clusters. The median probability values of teams in Clusters 2, 3, 4 and 5 are all over 99%, while Cluster 1 has a median probability value of 97.35%. These statistics would suggest that the majority of teams in each cluster have an attacking style that is clearly defined by the cluster to which it belongs. There are exceptions to this as some teams find themselves with almost equal belonging to two clusters, suggesting their style either varied across the season sampled or that they have a unique style of play that falls in between those defined by the clustering. The teams that do not have a high probability of belonging to one of the clusters will be considered individually during this section.

To discover how the cluster translates into the styles on the pitch, the average value for each attacking variable was found for teams in each cluster and then compared to the average values for all teams in the sample. The values for each cluster were then compared to the averages to discover how their style of play differs in the data and translates to an interpretable style of play. The styles of play are described below.

6.1.1 Cluster 1

The first cluster, those teams with the darker blue points in Figure 5.3, has some standout variables that suggest the style of play of teams in this cluster resembles counter-attacking football. This style involves allowing teams to come towards them on the pitch, and then moving the ball quickly and directly up the pitch to counterattack the opposition (Bangsbo and Peitersen, 2000). The data show that teams in this cluster are the most direct, have high dribbling rates but have higher than average possession in the defensive third of the pitch. Equally, this cluster has the highest proportion of shots taken inside the box. Combining this with the high directness and the high proportion of possession in the defensive third, this suggests an attacking style that moves quickly from the defensive third of the pitch to the attacking third, resulting in shots close to the goal. Furthermore, lower than average use of long balls and higher than average use of smart and simple passes differentiates this cluster from a long ball style that seeks to move the ball quickly using high passes and launches. A higher-than-average proportion of accelerations suggest players move the ball quickly down the pitch through carries, rather than passes. This style has been defined but there is little information on the key performance indicators for this style (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016). For this reason, there is a lack of quantitative research to which this research can be compared to. Based on the definition that exists in the literature, this style can be defined as counterattacking.

6.1.2 Cluster 2

The second cluster contains teams that play with a typical long ball style. The key metrics for teams in this cluster are passes from the defensive third to the attacking third and possession in the defensive third. This is combined with a below average number of accelerations, suggesting the ball is not moved forward by players with the ball, choosing instead to play passes. The percentage of simple passes is the lowest of all styles found by the clustering in this experiment, likewise for percentage of smart passes. This reinforces the idea of the style of play of teams in this cluster focusing on long balls. One surprising observation with this cluster is that the directness measure is below average. This mirrors the existing description of what is considered ‘direct’ attacking football, a style characterised by a preference of long passes over short and moving the ball quickly up the pitch, low number of touches per ball involvement and is one of the most commonly described attacking styles (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016). This is also most similar to what Muller (2022) describes as the ‘Bunker’ style, teams of this style have high rates of possession in their defensive third, carry the ball less than other styles (shown by low accelerations and directness). It has been described in various ways, including ‘direct’, and ‘kick and rush’ football (Bangsbo

and Peitersen, 2000). This would suggest that this research has discovered a known attacking style that has been described in the literature.

6.1.3 Cluster 3

Teams in the third cluster have the highest simple pass percentage of all clusters, as well as the highest smart pass percentage, possession in the middle third and possession in the final third. This describes a style of team that dominates possession, places a high emphasis on passing, particularly short simple passes, and does not often play in its defensive third. Despite this, these teams have higher rates of riskier actions such as smart passes and accelerations and ball carries. This suggests a combination of both direct and possession styles, the two styles most commonly described in the literature (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016). The style of teams in this cluster does not closely match to any pre-defined styles in the literature, with the exception of the ‘controlled’ style in Muller (2022). This style has low crossing scores, low width, a high percentage of short passes and has high possession in the attacking third of the pitch, all measures shared by findings in this research. As well as this, a high proportion of shots happen inside the box, and the accelerations metric for cluster 3 is also the highest out of any cluster, meaning that players often move the ball quickly with the ball. One interesting aspect of this style is that teams using this style favour playing centrally as opposed to down the wings, this is also reflected in low crossing statistics. As expected, given the particularly high number of simple and smart passes, the number of long balls played by teams in this cluster is the lowest out of all teams sampled.

6.1.4 Cluster 4

Cluster 4 is slightly less interpretable. There is very low directness, a low percentage of smart passes, low dribbles and accelerations and low possession in the final third. However, use of long balls is also low. The two distinctive features of this style are a preference for simple passes and possession in the middle of the pitch, both horizontally and vertically. The high percentage of simple passes and low scores in most other variables suggests a style of play that focuses on passing and possession and moves the ball slowly up the pitch. This is shown in the low acceleration’s metric, low directness score and low long ball score, as well as a very low possession score in the final third of the pitch. Interestingly, this is also the smallest cluster, only containing 9 of the 98 teams sampled.

A style focusing on possession involves more slow play and does not seek to take risks with passing, resulting in lower attempted through balls and long passes, which

are typically riskier (Hewitt et al., 2016). This suggests teams in this cluster play with a big focus on possession, looking to keep the ball and avoid riskier actions. This is shown in the data.

6.1.5 Cluster 5

The characteristics of teams in cluster 5 suggest the style of play is very end to end. Firstly, possession is high in the defensive third and the attacking third and low in the middle third. There is a high use of passes from defence to attack and midfield to attack, suggesting a preference for passes that move the ball between thirds, rather than within the same section of the pitch. Furthermore, the rates of dribbles and accelerations are high for these teams. Another significant aspect of this style of play is that play is focused down the wings and the use of crosses is high. The percentage of simple and smart passes are below average, as is the possession in the middle part of the pitch. Demonstrating this style of play moves the ball quickly from the defensive third to the attacking third, but using much more varied methods than other clusters, such as Cluster 2 that relies on long passes. Reilly (2011) define a ‘crossing’ style of play that is similar to the style of teams in this cluster due to their preference for playing in the wide areas of the pitch and the high use of crosses. Despite this, labelling this cluster based on the use of crosses would be reductive in this case as it would ignore other interesting aspects of this style, such as the high proportion of possession in both the defensive third and the attacking third. Equally, despite meeting several criteria of the definition of end-to-end style in Muller (2022), this label would ignore the propensity for crossing and using width. This style is a combination of the two, with defining features of both end-to-end football and high use of width.

6.2 Investigating Patterns of Teams in Each Cluster

Part of the methodology of this research was to omit any statistics that reflected outcomes or success. The reason for this was to avoid the algorithm matching teams based on ability, rather than style. Despite this, there were some interesting results regarding the calibre of teams in each cluster. The teams in each cluster were then analysed using the position they finished in their respective league in the season sampled (2017/18). 13 teams were relegated, either from finishing in the bottom three positions in the league in Serie A, the Premier League and La Liga, or the bottom two positions in the Bundesliga and Ligue 1. Of these 13, six belonged to Cluster 2 and five belonged to Cluster 5. The remaining two belonged to Cluster 4. There is

no dominating style of play for teams that found themselves relegated. Cluster 2, for example, also contains several teams that finished in the top half of their respective leagues. This includes Schalke 04, who finished second in the Bundesliga. The league positions for teams in Cluster 5 range from fifth to twentieth, also suggesting that style of play is not necessarily indicative of team success. The exception to this, however, is found in Cluster 3. This cluster contains four of the five league winners of this season. Furthermore, there are no teams in this cluster who finished below sixth in their league. This success is also reflected in other competitions. In the Champions League, Europe's premier football competition, which contains teams from many other leagues than those considered here, six of the eight quarter finalists belonged to Cluster 3. These findings suggest that while style of play is not a particularly good indicator of whether a team will perform poorly, there does seem to be a style that correlates with success, that of the teams in Cluster 3. This is especially interesting given that outcome statistics such as shots on target, goals and possession were omitted to avoid clusters being inherently better or worse than others. Despite this, it is clear that Cluster 3 includes teams that perform better than others. This could suggest that this is the most effective attacking style of play. Alternatively, it could suggest that this style of attacking football requires the highest quality players to play it, meaning it is beyond the capability of other teams.

Another interesting aspect of these results is the prevalence of these styles in each league. All clusters contain teams from Serie A, Ligue 1, and La Liga. These leagues contain teams that represent each of the five styles found by this research. This is not the case with the Premier League and the Bundesliga. Cluster 5 does not contain any Bundesliga teams, while Cluster 4 does not contain any Premier League teams. This shows that, in the sample at least, playing styles do vary from league to league. However, the leagues considered do not appear to have a dominant style.

6.3 The Inbetweeners: Teams with Low Probability of Belonging to a Cluster

Chelsea had a 50.2% probability of belonging to Cluster 1 and a 49.9% probability of belonging to Cluster 3. When comparing their data to the cluster averages and the overall average, it is clear that the team shares many of the traits of both styles. Chelsea ranks above average for directness and possession in the defensive third, both characteristics of teams in Cluster 1, as well as possession in the final third which is a characteristic of Cluster 3. Furthermore, Chelsea's style of play includes many characteristics that are shared by Clusters 1 and 3: simple pass percentage, smart pass percentage and accelerations. This could suggest a style of play not captured by the

techniques used in this research, proving that styles beyond the five found here exist in football. However, this particular style is unique to Chelsea in this analysis.

Brighton Hove Albion was also placed in Cluster 1 by the model (52.8% probability) but also had a 47.1% probability of belonging to Cluster 5. This seems mainly to be due to above average wide play statistics such as crossing and possession in wide areas, which are characteristics of Cluster 5, while also ranking highly for key aspects of Cluster 1, such as directness and possession in the defensive third. Again, this style is an outlier in this analysis and unique to Brighton Hove Albion.

The final team that does not appear likely to belong to one cluster are Southampton. Southampton has a probability of belonging to Cluster 5 of 56.9% and a probability of 42.9% of belonging to Cluster 1. While similar to the teams above, who appeared to play with a unique style, Southampton changed manager during this season, unlike the others. This could suggest a change of style due to this change. This could, of course, apply to the other teams in this section. The results are based on an average over a season. Within this season, teams can try to play in different styles with different formations, regardless of management changes. The fact that these teams do not fit definitively into any cluster could suggest a unique style, or just a style that has changed and evolved throughout the season. In order to answer this question, the data would have to be broken down to a match-level granularity and styles determined on this level and then changes tracked over the course of the season. This level of detail is beyond the scope of this paper and would be inefficient using a data set of this size.

6.4 This Research in the Academic Environment

The styles of play found here do not form an exhaustive list, nor do they all exist in all leagues. Having noted that, one criticism of previous work in this area is the small sample of data used. For example, Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016) considered a small sample of games from incomplete sections of two seasons of Spanish and English elite football. Lago-Peñas et al. (2017) considered just one season of the Chinese Soccer Super League. Decroos et al. (2018) considers just the English Premier League in 2015/16, a league that does not contain one of the styles of attacking football found in this analysis. This research uses the largest public collection of football data available, therefore improving on the weaknesses that exist in the literature (Pappalardo et al., 2019). This is important in the context of this research, as using data from more leagues and countries provides a much more holistic view of football and thus will result in findings that are more applicable to the sport, rather than the unique properties of the leagues considered. An obvious next step for research in this area is, therefore, to conduct a similar analysis on a data set that includes more leagues and teams, across

a variety of countries.

A major limitation to this study, and this area of research in general, is the lack of consistency regarding variables used to define attacking football. There is no consensus regarding performance indicators for each style, so each investigation into this field varies (Fernandez-Navarro et al., 2016). Furthermore, the data used also varies. The use of count data, as used in this research, has been criticised in favour of sectioning matches into phases and sequences for a finer granularity. While using spatial data does improve on other investigations, this data set does not include player positional data, instead only tracking the location of events involving the ball. With positional data, more sophisticated techniques could be used such as using Voronoi cells, to see how player positions and controlled spaces impact attacking styles (Raudonius and Allmendinger, 2021). Likewise, player positional data can be used to include team formation data (Van Haaren et al., 2015). In the future, with the progress made in data collection through developments such as the FIFA Football Language, the consistency and availability of data could translate to a more consistent approach in academia surrounding this topic (FIFA, 2021).

Furthermore, situational context was ignored in this study, which has previously been recommended in the literature due to its importance in sports performance (Lago-Peñas et al., 2017). Variables such as match location, opposition level and score line were not considered. Furthermore, one contextual data point that was excluded was whether a club changed head coach or manager during a season. This could have a substantial impact on style of play and result in two different styles of play occurring throughout a season. This was excluded due to the high number of changes that exist across these teams. Approximately half the teams would have had to be excluded had this factor been included in the analysis.

6.5 Implications to the Football Industry

This research has the potential to impact football in useful ways. Firstly, teams can use the results of this research to understand the style of play of potential opposition, as well as cross-referencing this information to see the style of attacking football that yields the best results against the style of the opposition. Another benefit is that players for transfers can be identified from teams with a similar style of attacking play, or from teams who play in a style that is to be emulated. These are the two main areas in which a club can benefit from using data analysis such as this. However, while this is useful in theory, the data considered is somewhat dated. This means that usefulness in terms of understanding the playing style of teams considered is limited as it does not show how teams currently play. The usefulness of this research

in practice is to provide a methodology and a data processing outline for conducting similar research and a demonstration of the results that can be obtained by doing so.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

This study sought to discover whether distinct styles of football could be found by conducting a clustering analysis on a large collection of football event data. Several attempts to do this existed in the literature already. These studies provided a methodological framework that guided this paper but also revealed areas of this academic field where research was limited. In particular, both Lago-Peñas et al. (2017) and Fernandez-Navarro et al. (2016) identified a lack of studies that quantitatively described and measured playing styles. This study was an attempt to fill that gap. The application of dimension reduction and clustering does not just provide a methodological framework for others looking to conduct similar analyses but is also transferrable to other sports data sets and unsupervised classification problems in general. The usefulness of UMAP as a dimension reduction technique in comparison with others, such as t-SNE and PCA, was discussed at length and its benefits used. Furthermore, a similar review of clustering was included and the case for using a probabilistic clustering method over a deterministic one was also put forward. This is important for further guiding research into attacking styles, as well as clustering analyses concerning subjects beyond sports.

In terms of results, the primary aim of the research was met. Five distinctive attacking styles were identified, each with specific defining features that mostly corroborate the literature. These styles are defined by counterattacking (cluster 1), direct play using long balls (cluster 2), a high possession ‘controlled’ style (cluster 3), a low-risk high possession style (cluster 4), and an end-to-end style (cluster 5). Most teams were found to have a high likeliness of belonging to one of these styles, with the exception of the Chelsea, Brighton Hove Albion, and Southampton. The secondary aims of the research were also met. There was a clear correlation between superior team performance in their respective leagues and attacking style. Four out of five league winners belonged to cluster 3 and this cluster had the highest average finishing

position by a distance. On the other hand, the worse performing teams did not necessarily have a style in common. This suggests that while no style is inherently worse than the others, in this particular season a style of play existed that resulted in better performance than the others. This style is that of the teams in cluster 3.

The limitations of this research were also considered. The first limitation is lack of comparability between similar studies due to inconsistent definitions of what attacking football is and of what variables it is comprised. While these definitions vary, so too will the results as the input data will be different in each case, regardless of methodology. Furthermore, the data sets used in different studies vary as well. Football is a game of constant development and evolution, meaning results can quickly become outdated. Finally, this research does not include contextual factors that can affect the style of play. These are aspects such as a change in manager or coaching team partway through a season, the importance of a particular game or the quality of the opposition. Finding a way to include these factors in a quantitative analysis of this size is problematic due to the qualitative nature of the contextual factors. For this reason, these were excluded from this study.

Despite these limitations, this research provides value to both the football industry and the academic community. As mentioned above, the methodological framework here can be applied by teams and football analysts themselves. With a more recent and relevant data set, these findings can guide coaching and training programmes, giving teams a potential advantage over rivals. Furthermore, understanding styles of play and which teams employ each style can inform transfer activity such as which players to target in order to play in a certain way. Both of these practical use cases can create an analytical edge for clubs that will provide both performance and financial benefits, demonstrating the business value in researching this topic, as well as the academic value.

Further study should look to standardise the definition of attacking football. This would provide a foundation for all future work in this area and enable a level of comparability and consistency that does not exist to this point. Furthermore, the use of phases, as suggested by Clijmans (2021), will also enhance the level of detail of the analysis and provide a more in depth understanding of attacking styles. As technology improves, it is likely the data streams extracted from football matches will also change. This makes the field of football data analytics an exciting area for research. Further studies will likely be able to leverage these improvements to allow much deeper analysis.

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